

ASILE

Global Asylum
Governance and
the European
Union's Role

Towards A Stylized Model of Dynamics on the Market for Smuggling Services

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIDA	Asylum Information Database
CCTE	Conditional Cash Transfer for Education
PMM	Presidency of Migration Management
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union''
ESSN	Emergency Social Safety Net
EURA	EU Readmission Agreement
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
FRIT	The Facility for Refugees in Turkey
GCR	The Global Compact on Refugees
IPA	Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance
IOM	International Organization for Migration
LFIP	Law on Foreigners and International Protection
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
PDMM	Provincial Directorate of Migration Management
TPR	Temporary Protection Regulation
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Emergency Fund
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A key assumption of European policy makers is that the introduction of migration restrictions reduces the volume of irregular migration. Our analysis addresses this assumption by looking at the spike of irregular migration on the Aegean in 2015-2016 through a stylized model. Our stylized model does not pretend to fully capture the decision-making process of either people in need of international protection or of people considering to act as smugglers. We have abstracted from many aspects which are known to be relevant.

Our model does allow us to examine the impact of restrictive migration policies. While policy makers and much of the academic literature assume that restrictive policies reduce the flow of migrants, our analysis shows that the restrictive measures which migrants and smugglers expect considerably *increase* the flow before the introduction of restrictive policy measures, while resulting in a *reduction* only after their enforcement. In other words, restrictive migration policies have ambiguous effects. On the one hand they result in spikes (perceived in 2015-2016 as a migration crisis), while on the other hand restrictive migration policies may contribute to a lower aggregate volume of migration in the long run.

This means that the peaking number of asylum seekers in Europe in 2015-2016 (resulting in the perceived migration crisis) were an unintended effect of restrictive European migration policies. If people in need of international protection would not have had reason to expect restrictive policy measures any moment, the peak of people crossing the Aegean would, according to our stylized model, have been at 70.000 people in the spring of 2016, instead of the 212.168 people who actually crossed in October 2015. This is an unintended effect of restrictive policy; this effect has been a key ingredient of the perceived migration crisis in 2015-2016.

According to our stylized model, if people in need of international protection would not have had reason to expect restrictive policies, the total number of people crossing the Aegean over the period 2015-2020 may have been up to 20 percent higher. However, this possibly larger number of people would have arrived more gradually, which would have been more manageable in terms of reception of asylum seekers, asylum procedures, and security checks.

And finally, according to our model, financially supporting hosting countries for providing humanitarian and socio-economical aid to refugees has reduced the number of people who were willing to pay a smuggler in order to travel to Europe. In other words, the effects of providing funding for refugees in Turkey has had unambiguous, positive effects on reducing the volume of irregular migration towards Europe and deaths at the borders.

1. Introduction

In 2015-2016, Europe witnessed a sharp increase and subsequent decrease (a ‘spike’) of migrants and refugees¹ on the so-called ‘Balkan-route’ from Turkey, via Greece and the Balkan countries, to the other EU Member States. The spike has led to considerable administrative and political challenges and revealed a systemic refugee protection crisis within the EU (Den Heijer, Rijpma & Spijkerboer 2016; Byrne, Noll, & Vedsted-Hansen, 2020). Therefore, it is important for policy makers to understand the processes leading to the beginning and end of the spike. This will allow them to assess the impact of policy interventions and possibly to prevent or reduce future spikes. It will also give insight into policy interventions which inadvertently may contribute to spikes.

Within the ASILE context, this research contributes to developing future asylum policies by focusing on a central element of the EU’s containment policies. A core assumption of these policies is that intensifying border control will reduce the number of migrants who succeed in reaching European territory. However, the recurrent ‘spikes’ in migrants reaching Europe by sea suggest that these policies have unintended effects, due to incompletely understood and acknowledged processes and mechanisms behind the occurrence of spikes. We investigate the idea that a stylized micro-economic model of the market for smuggling services may contribute to a more complete understanding of the ‘spikes’. This contributes to developing more effective policy responses to the presence of migrants in need of international protection at European borders.

1.1. Conceptual framework

The approach in this report is inspired by the observation that previous ‘migration crises’ had a characteristic similar to the 2015-2016 situation on the Aegean: a sharp increase and sharp decrease, be it at lower absolute levels and with different time spans (Figures 1-3, *infra*). The Canary Islands had a spike in 2006, the Central Mediterranean in 2008, 2011 and 2014-2016, the Aegean in October 2015.

¹ Throughout, for brevity, we will use “migrants” instead of “migrants and refugees”.

Figure 1: Migrants arriving at the Canary Islands irregularly between 1994 and 2012

Source: Godenau 2014.

Figure 2: Maritime migrants arriving in Italy 1997-2019

Source: Spina 2020.

Figure 3: Monthly maritime arrivals on the Greek islands 2015-2017

Source: Spijkerboer 2016, based on UNHCR data.

This observation suggests that, although obviously the context of each spike was specific, more general structural processes may be at work. While the context of future inflows will again be different, a better understanding of possible general mechanisms will help policy makers to create and implement faster and more effective responses to migration, especially if the said general mechanisms lead to important behavioural responses to policy interventions, that too may share important features over different contexts and that may become better predictable when the underlying mechanisms are explicitly taken into consideration.

Literature seeking to explain the changing volume of migration (the issues at the core of the current report) focuses on long-term trends. This is the case also for analyses of what has been named 'irregular migration' such as Massey, Durand & Pren (2014). Particularly with regard to forced migration theory on the temporal dimension is limited, and explanations such as developed in general migration theory (Massey et al. 1999) are absent in forced migration studies (Fitzgerald 2018, Fiddian-Qasmiyeh, Loescher, Long & Sigona 2014). These two gaps intersect in the current study, which is about *short-term* developments in predominantly *forced* migration (the 2015 spike was predominantly made up of Syrian refugees). The present study seeks to begin to bridge this gap by (1) relying on hypotheses from migration studies (see De Haas et al. 2019 for a state-of-the-art overview) so as to make these fruitful in the context of short-term forced migration spikes and (2) relying on a micro-economic analytical framework which is eminently suitable for understanding short-term market dynamics in the market for smuggling services. On both points, this distinguishes our approach from existing research.

1.1.1. Hypotheses from migration studies

By going beyond approaches based only on push and pull factors and rational choice theory, migration studies rely on a comprehensive framework so as to explain migration and asylum more adequately than push-pull² and rational choice³ approaches alone are capable of (De Haas et al. 2019). Central notions in more elaborate modelling frameworks are migration aspirations, migration capabilities and the role of intermediate systems. In our context, the notions of migration aspirations and capabilities include the aspirations and capabilities of refugees and asylum seekers.

The notion of *migration aspirations* can be illustrated by the example of Syrians. Before the eruption of the conflict in Syria in 2011, Syrian emigration was relatively low. The aspirations of Syrians to migrate changed drastically as a result of the conflict. In order to explain the onward movement of Syrians from neighboring countries to countries further away (including the EU), the availability of reception in the region (i.e. in the country of origin and in neighboring countries) needs to be taken into account as well. Whereas the security and socio-economic situation in Syria is crucial for explaining the aspiration to leave Syria, the (security but in particular) socio-economic situation of Syrian refugees in neighboring countries is arguably crucial for understanding the aspiration to leave those countries and move onward to Europe.

In addition to these aspirations, in which issues commonly referred to as push-pull factors play an important role, *migration capabilities* are crucial. People will only be able to act on their aspirations if they also have the necessary capabilities to migrate. They need financial and social resources (networks, but also personal characteristics like physical strength and resourcefulness). The resources required for moving to the preferred destination countries in Europe are related to migration restrictions (such as visa requirements and border controls), which make migration more expensive, tougher and riskier. The capability to migrate can be expected to diminish to the extent that these costs of migration (i.e., migration restrictions) increase.

There are two dominant *intermediate systems* – in addition to the aspirations and capabilities – that shape the migration volume:

1. group strategies (of households and ethnic/religious/national groups);
2. demand-supply interactions on the market for smuggling services.

Ad. 1) As to the group strategies, at least three factors are expected to impact migration decisions, routes and destinations. *First*, households will typically try to spread risks by having household members in different countries or regions. *Second*, households will generally select members with the highest aspirations and the largest capabilities. *Third*, somewhat contradictory to the first factor at the larger group level, the presence of group members *en route* or in destination countries may affect not only the aspiration to migrate, but crucially also affects capability to migrate to countries where these group members reside. Network effect approaches suggest an inverted U-shape of migration patterns of particular groups: the first group members will function as bridgeheads, but when their absorption capacity is saturated, they will become gatekeepers for future

² For critiques of push-pull approaches see Carrera et al. 2020, 11-12; James & Mayblin 2016; Guild 2021.

³ For critiques of rational choice approaches see Crawley & Hagen-Zanker 2018; Crawley & Jones 2021; İçduygu 2021.

migrants. For all three elements, the gender and age composition of migrant groups is indicative. Among refugees, a large influx is related to a representative age and gender distribution (comp. Spijkerboer 2000, p. 24-25). We initially aimed to map group strategies by analyzing the demographic composition of the migrants using the Balkan route, but our data did not allow us to develop this aspect.

Ad. 2) A second dominant intermediate system which shapes migration volumes is arguably 'the market for smuggling services' (Auriol & Mesnard 2012; Mandić 2017a). Where the above mentioned role of group- and household strategies in shaping migration volumes has already been extensively discussed in the academic literature (Massey 1990), relatively little attention has so far been awarded to the role of human smugglers. In particular, the attention for economic aspects of the human smuggling market is limited (Kleemans and Smit 2014; but see Naiditch & Vranceanu 2020), let alone the relation between these economic aspects and (sudden) changes in 'migration volumes'. For this reason, in this study we will dedicate specific attention to this issue.

1.1.2. Hypotheses from the market for smuggling services

For analyzing the smuggling market, we aim to draw parallels with models of dynamic competitive market equilibrium for exhaustible resources, developed in environmental and natural resource economics, for which Hotelling (1931) has provided the conceptual basis. The analytical parallels between both cases will become clearer as we proceed, but can be sketched as follows. The finite stock of potential migrants compares to the finite stock of the natural resource. In a market for a natural resource, each unit of the stock extracted by a resource owner, is no longer available for extraction in the future. As a result, resource owners respond to current, but also to expected future prices. They not only decide whether to extract and supply their resources to the market, but also when. Demand for the resource from consumers depends negatively on the price: low prices attract consumers whereas high prices discourage them from buying the resource. Similarly, in a market for smuggling services, each migrant transferred today can no longer be transferred in the future. Hence, migrants respond to current but also to expected future prices, thus deciding not only on whether to cross, but also when. The supply of smuggling services depends positively on the price: smugglers enter when prices are high (e.g. early in a spike) and drop out of the market when prices are low. Therefore, even though the contexts are very different, the analytical framework that we apply can and will benefit considerably from earlier dynamic modelling advances in the environmental economics field.

The market for smuggling services generally has the following characteristics (i.a. Baird 2015, Brachet 2018, Campana 2018, Lucht 2013):

- both supply and demand originate from large numbers of relatively isolated actors, all small relative to the market, so that competitive market conditions apply (there are no cartels or centrally coordinated supply or demand strategies etc.);
- suppliers of smuggling services usually have another business (fishing, phone cards) from which they can relatively easily access the market, and to which they can return if profitability drops; this makes entry-exit barriers relatively low and supply flexible ("elastic", meaning that mild changes in expected profitability already generate in- or outflow of suppliers);

- the investments required from suppliers for entering the market are relatively small, resulting in constant marginal cost of smuggling services, consistent with a constant opportunity cost of labor;
- demand concerns a one-time, one-directional service; e.g. migrants who travelled from Turkey to Greece are highly unlikely to want to do so again, and do not want to travel back and forth on a regular basis; in economic terms, this means that demand is exhaustive/finite; this is a relevant characteristic even if the demand is huge as it impacts the dynamic behavior both at the demand and supply side of the market.

These market characteristics imply that, if demand (resulting from the combination of aspirations and capabilities) increases, one expects prices (and hence profit margins) to first go up, but then to rapidly attract more supply and increase competition (Czaika & de Haas 2017). In a dynamic process, in which seasonal effects as well as migrant perceptions (of the likelihood of success, anticipated restrictive policies, etc.) play an important role too, more supply will in turn result in lower prices, resulting in a further sustaining of effective demand (as prices go down, the capability of more people will be sufficient to act on their aspirations). In a normal market, with stable demand conditions (think of the demand for apples, that for a given consumers typically does not become saturated over the years if incomes and tastes remain the same), one would expect a stable equilibrium to develop. But, in a dynamic market of one-time services, and possibly even more so with uncertainty about future conditions, the market processes may be quite volatile.

Part of these dynamics can be that an anticipated future restrictive policy measure may lead to more demand in the shorter term, paralleling the so-called green paradox (Sinn 2012; Van der Ploeg and Withagen 2012). The EU-Turkey Statement on March 18, 2016 on restricting passages may well have had this effect (Ovacik, Ineli-Ciger, Ulusoy, & Spijkerboer, 2022; Yüksel, 2022). The plan for the EU-Turkey statement was launched by the Dutch member of parliament Diederik Samsom on 28 January 2016, and the news of this spread quickly on (social) media. This may, for example, explain the minor spike in the week of 24 February 2016 (see Figure 4), assuming that migrants as well as providers of smuggling services needed some time to mobilize resources to speed up their intention to (facilitate) crossing from Turkey to the Greek islands.

Figure 4: Weekly maritime arrivals on the Greek islands 2015-2016

Source: Spijkerboer 2016, based on UNHCR data.

2. Methodology

Our study thus seeks to contribute innovative and multi-disciplinary elements to several widely discussed issues in the migration and migration policy domains. It aims to analyze these topics by developing and analyzing a stylized microeconomic model of the smuggling market. The notion of the smuggling market refers to the fact that some people (suppliers of smuggling services) may offer smuggling services, and that others (migrants) may use these services. Partly because smuggling services are prohibited, but also because the determinants of demand can vary rapidly, the dynamics on this market may be volatile; the spikes (supra) suggest that they indeed are.

The methodology of the research contains complex elements such as transferring qualitative datasets from migration studies to quantitative input for the dynamic economic model. The following will provide an overview of methodological issues relating to data collection and the development of the model.

2.1. Period and region

Our research focuses on a very specific period that deeply affected the public and academic discussions in Europe. Between 2015 and 2017, more than 2 million migrants entered the EU, one million of which entered through the southeastern maritime borders, namely Greece⁴. This triggered a wide range of political and societal reactions in Europe, including reshaping the asylum and migration policy instruments of the EU states. During this period, the eastern maritime borders of the EU, i.e., the Aegean Sea between Turkey and Greece, became the target of new policy approaches. This makes the region, during the said period, a suitable case for developing and applying a stylized microeconomic model. Between 2015 and 2017, all major international organizations (such as UNHCR and IOM), EU agencies (Europol and Frontex) and civil society organizations were present in the Aegean Sea region. These organizations regularly produced and published reports, thus creating a comprehensive, (mostly) publicly available qualitative and quantitative data environment.

2.2. Data Collection

After identifying the required data for the model, we started to gather, clean, and compile the publicly available data. However, while there is an abundance of accessible data for this period and region, most of the data is not (directly) useable. Most of the datasets collected and compiled by organizations such as UNHCR and IOM do not include metadata, i.e. information about datasets including data collection methodologies. Furthermore, there are inconsistencies and unclarities in the terminology within the datasets. And finally, often the data from the same organization is inconsistent; it seems that older versions of datasets remain in circulation without information on the edition or version.

After the initial data collection phase, the research team identified existing data and identified the missing data. As a following step, researchers approached experts, academics, inter-governmental agencies and international organizations to map and

⁴ International Organization for Migration (IOM), Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM); <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/yearly-compilation-of-arrivals-to-europe>.

gather data that is not publicly available. Unfortunately, several organizations, including Frontex and the EU Asylum Agency (EUAA) did not respond to our repeated requests, while the Europol European Migrant Smuggling Centre (EMSC) informed us that “the topic does not link directly to the work” of this unit.⁵

2.3. Modeling and terminology

Developing a stylized microeconomic model of the smuggling market naturally required certain decisions on how to use and transfer data from migration studies to economic analysis. Most of the definitions and adaptations are identified and discussed within the respective paragraphs below. In this paragraph, we provide a justification of some unorthodox and arguably more debatable choices.

For the purposes of this report, migration is defined as a single, one-way human movement from the source to the host country.⁶ There were two main reasons behind this definition. First, during the focused period, 2015-2017, more than 1 million individuals entered the EU.

Second, in the literature there is a growing body of work dealing with the decision-making processes of the migrants (Campana & Gelsthorpe, 2021; Crawley & Hagen-Zanker, 2018; İçduygu, 2021; Wissink, Düvell, & van Eerdewijk, 2013). The decision-making processes do not take place in vacuum and do not follow a predictable process. There are countless multi-dimensional factors impacting the decision and migration trajectories. Nonetheless, throughout the model, we treat migration as an eventually binary choice: to move or not. This methodological choice was made to limit the number of exogenous and endogenous variables. In reality, the variable (i.e., the decision to move or not) is unique and complex for each individual and therefore cannot be deterministically quantified *ex ante*. However, when individual decisions are analyzed at the level of the entire group, generalizations can be made and individuals' choice of behavior can eventually be limited to the binary choice of whether to stay or to move. We can and will represent differences between individuals by allowing for aggregate heterogeneity: the critical values of variables such as policy restrictions and prices for which individuals change between 'staying' and 'moving' will follow a distribution over individuals. With this assumption, available statistical data can be used to calibrate the model. This approach should not be understood as ignoring or rejecting the existing literature on the decision-making processes of the people on the move, but rather to keep the reasons why people make different choices under different circumstances exogenous to (i.e. determined outside) the model through the Aegean region⁷. The composition of this group was mixed in terms of both policy relevance and migration motives: it included refugees, asylum seekers, migrants, people enjoying temporary protection in Turkey as well as people engaging in so-called secondary movements. Distinguishing the different motivations and characteristics of people on the move would make it practically impossible to develop a model. Therefore, all individuals on the move will be gathered under one term as “migrants”, and the process will be described as “migration”. This terminology should not be understood as limiting or altering the widely accepted definitions of refugee, migrant or asylum seeker.

⁵ Email by representative of Europol to the authors of 21 April 2021, on file with authors.

⁶ Hence, we exclude migrants that go back and forth on a regular basis, such as seasonal workers.

⁷ International Organization for Migration (IOM), Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM); <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/yearly-compilation-of-arrivals-to-europe>.

2.4. Economics terminology

Throughout the report, terms from the economics discipline will be used to describe certain elements of the model such as “migration flow”, “costs of migration” or “utility of migration” and “willingness to pay for migration”. We are aware that such reductive terminology risks losing sight of the devastating concerns and circumstances that individual migrants have and face, and in a way that is what using a microeconomic model describing aggregate patterns unavoidably does. However, we will show below that our approach can create insights in the consequences which public policy decisions can have for migrants, and can thus be helpful to reduce human suffering. We do not claim that the reductive assumptions that will be described below (Section 4) reflect all human reality of migrants, but we do argue that they enable us to reflect on the possible inhuman effects of European policies. The aim of this research is to analyze the impact of policy changes on the number of people crossing borders in circumstances that threaten their lives. In doing so, we seek to build on earlier research on border deaths.⁸

⁸ For an overview see www.borderdeaths.org.

3. Literature review

In this section we review the relevant theoretical literature about migration, with a focus on literature from economics. We will make a distinction between dynamic and static analyses and between studies that focus on economic motives (such as wage differences between countries) and those that emphasize other motives, such as political conflicts and wars, to migrate.

3.1. Dynamic models

There is a small theoretical literature about the economics of (irregular) migration. Most of these studies are casted in a static setting. Only several papers explicitly take migration dynamics into account. Typically, the analysis starts from an economic motive to migrate, instead of wars or environmental disasters in migrants' home countries. In an early contribution, Djajić (1987) studies the interaction between the labor markets of two countries, which are interconnected because of (in Djajić's terminology) illegal migration

In a related paper, motivated by efforts to counter illegal immigration into the US – such as *Operation Gatekeeper* in the San Diego area in 1994 – Djajić (1999) builds a dynamic model of irregular migration to examine the effects of tighter border control policies and internal enforcement measures on the stock of illegal immigrants. Migration in the model is driven by the wage differential between the source and the destination country. The destination country determines the penalties for employers with illegal workers, chooses expenditures on border control, and on the detection, apprehension, detention, and deportation of illegal workers. Migrants can invest in anti-detection measures. They can either work in agriculture, close to the border, or in manufacturing further inland. In this setting, Djajić (1999) shows that tighter border control measures may result in a larger stock of illegal migrants, as they increase anti-detection efforts by migrants. Furthermore, he demonstrates that once enforcement in agriculture near the border reaches a certain threshold, immigrants move to the manufacturing further inland. There, they form networks which serve to increase the expected income of new immigrants, at least for a certain range of illegal workers in the sector. The result may be that tighter border control policies or internal enforcement measures in agriculture ultimately result in a larger stock of illegal migrants.

The recent study by Brausmann & Djajić (2022) is more closely related to our work, as migrants in their model are motivated to leave their home country because of an armed conflict or environmental issues, instead of for economic reasons.⁹ They build a dynamic model of mass migration from a source country through a transit country to a final-destination country, with a focus on the interaction between the behavior of migrants and the authorities of the destination country.

Brausmann & Djajić (2022) make the following assumptions. Per unit of time a constant, exogenous fraction of the migrants in the transit country attempts to cross to the destination country. Resources spent on border control by the destination country

⁹ There are some other recent theoretical, dynamic migration studies such as Djajić (2013) and Akay et al. (2021). These are only laterally connected to our work, though, as they focus on capital accumulation and savings behaviour.

negatively affect the probability of crossing successfully and positively affect the costs of an attempt to cross the border. Furthermore, the total amount of people trying to cross the border at a particular moment in time positively affects the probability of crossing successfully, but also the costs of an attempt to cross. The inflow of people in the transit country depends positively on the probability of crossing successfully and negatively on the costs of a crossing attempt. Finally, the amount of resources allocated for border control increases (decreases) over time if the number of migrants is larger (smaller) than a prespecified target level.

Brausmann & Djajić (2022) apply their model, like we do, to the Syrian refugee crisis of 2015. They show that the speed of adjustment of border control expenditures is crucial for the costs of bringing back the flow of migrants back to the target level. The lower the speed of gradually increasing expenditures or the longer the delay before suddenly scaling up expenditures, the higher the total costs. Furthermore, they show that criminalization of human smuggling activity in the transit country increases the effectiveness of border control expenditures. Finally, it is demonstrated that the presence of diaspora in the destination country increases the long-run amount of migrants in the transit country and the long-run expenditure on border control in the destination country.

Our work crucially differs from Brausmann & Djajić (2022) in several dimensions. First, migrants in our model decide whether to cross and, if so, when. These decisions depend on current and expected future policies. In Brausmann & Djajić (2022), however, a constant fraction of migrants leaves the transit country in each period, irrespective of policy measures. In their setting, migrants are not optimizing nor forward-looking, implying that the decision whether and when to leave is not modeled. Second, we compare the real-world outcome in the presence of actual policies with a counterfactual 'no-policy' scenario, whereas Brausmann & Djajić (2022) consider the policy response by the destination country to be endogenous by assuming that border control expenditures increase (decrease) over time as long as the migration flow is above (below) a certain target level.

3.2. Static models

Apart from the literature that explicitly accounts for the dynamics of migration, there is a substantial static literature. By and large, contributions in this field focus on economically motivated migration and restrict attention to the effect of migrants on labor market outcomes such as the relative wage of skilled and unskilled workers, unemployment rates and 'brain drains'. See, e.g. Ethier (1986); Hill (1987); Hill and Pearce (1990); Djajić et al. (2012); Djajić et al. (2016);

Fernández-Huertas Moraga & Rapoport (2014) argue that providing visas to workers from poor countries contributes to global poverty alleviation. However, in a non-cooperative situation destination countries ignore this positive externality. This results in under-provision of visas. They show that the creation of a market for tradable immigration quotas (TIQs), coupled with a matching system between migrants and destination countries, helps to internalize the policy alleviation externality and considerably increases the cost-effectiveness of the allocation of migrants over destinations, in the sense that total costs of hosting migrants go down.

Transit migration

Czaika (2009) allows for an economic motive to migrate, but in his model migrants primarily leave their home country because of disutility from persecution. Migrants have three options to choose from: (i) stay in the conflict affected home country; (ii) migrate with negligible costs to a neighboring first-asylum country where security is guaranteed but economic conditions are worse; or (iii) migrate at high costs to a Western industrialized country with better economic conditions but with the risk of being rejected and deported to the home country. In this setting, Czaika (2009) shows that relatively less persecuted people seek asylum in Western countries, to avoid the risk of being deported to the home country. Moreover, he demonstrates that neighboring countries and Western countries end up in a race of restrictive asylum policies. Finally, it is shown in the paper that refugee-related aid transfers to neighboring first-asylum countries may be an effective instrument to reduce the level of migration to Western countries.

Djajić & Michael (2014) consider a game between a destination and a transit country to examine how much the destination country should pay the transit country to strengthen its immigration controls and how much of this money will actually be used by the transit country for immigration control. They determine the Nash equilibrium of the game and use it to derive three main policy conclusions. First, if immigration control spending in the transit country becomes more effective (e.g. because of technical change), the destination country should increase its transfers to the transit country, even if the latter uses a smaller fraction of these transfers for border control. Second, if preferences in the transit country change towards being more restrictive with respect to migration, transfers to the transit country should be increased. Finally, an increase in migration towards the destination country calls for an increase in transfers to the transit country, even if this requires a cut in spending for its own border control.

In related work, Djajić (2017) looks at the effectiveness of immigration policies in transit and final destination countries. He shows that stricter internal enforcement measures to reduce undocumented migration are more effective when applied in the transit country than when applied at the final destination. This difference in effectiveness is larger the higher are the costs of going from the transit to the final destination country. Furthermore, while more stringent internal enforcement measures in the transit country increase the effectiveness of border controls in the final destination country relative to those of the transit country, implementing more stringent measures in the destination country does not affect the relative effectiveness of border controls across the transit and destination country. These findings suggest that there are potential gains from cooperation between transit and destination countries.

Smuggling market

Tamura (2010) examines the effect of policies to combat smuggling. He models a migrant smuggling market where smugglers differ in terms of the capacity to exploit migrants in the destination country. The paper shows that countries with limited sources that want to eliminate smuggling should focus on apprehension of smugglers at the border instead of inland. The latter induces a shift to nonexploitative smuggling and hence is less effective in terms of reducing the total amount of smuggled people into the country. (Tamura, 2013) extends this analysis with asymmetric information about a smuggler's capacity to exploit migrants in the destination country. This results in the potential existence of an adverse selection equilibrium where only exploitative smugglers are active and it may lower the effectiveness

of border apprehension of migrants and smugglers. Improved inland apprehension may even be counter effective in terms of reducing migrant exploitation.

Naiditch and Vranceanu (2020) propose a search and matching model à la Pissarides (1985) of the smuggling market, where migrants and smugglers search for each other and are matched with a probability depending on frictions in the market, such as the number of migrants per smuggler. They show that an increase of smuggling costs reduces the number of smugglers, the amount successful matches and the number of migrants that reach the destination country in the short run. The model may generate an inverted-U-shaped relationship between the (exogenous) probability of reaching the destination country and the welfare of migrants. The reason for the turning point is that a high probability of success drives up the equilibrium fee that smugglers can ask.

Debt-financing versus self-financing

Friebel and Guriev (2006) examine the effect of debt financing of migration by intermediaries. In order to borrow the money needed for illegal migration, migrants without collateral typically enter a debt/labor contract with an intermediary, in which they commit themselves to work in the destination country for the intermediary until the debt is paid off. However, if migrants are able to switch from the illegal to the legal sector they will receive protection from the host country. This enables them to default on their debt. As a result, policies that make it more costly or risky to move from the illegal to the legal sector, such as stricter deportation policies, benefit the intermediaries. Hence, these policies may result in an increase in the flow of relatively unskilled illegal migrants financed by debt/labor contracts and a decrease in the flow of relatively skilled self-financed migrants.

In a related study, Djajić & Vinogradova (2014) show that debt/labor contracts are only chosen by liquidity constrained migrants if the wage differential between the destination and source country is sufficiently large compared to the migration costs. Furthermore, they show that both stricter border controls and internal enforcement measures in the destination country reduce the amount of migrants with a debt/labor contract compared to self-financed migrants. Nevertheless, these policies do not necessarily lower the total inflow of migrants, especially from countries with sufficiently high local wages.

Regular versus irregular migration

Djajić (2014) explore whether migrants in a transit country prefer to reach their ultimate destination with the aid of human smugglers or by applying for resettlement with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). He shows that relatively young, skilled and wealthy migrants with access to credit from their family network are likely to prefer the smuggling option. The reason is this option is riskier in the sense that it has higher up-front costs but also higher expected benefits. In the case of a failure, migrants have to return to their home country and pay off their debt. This is less problematic for young, skilled and wealthy migrants.

Djajić & Vinogradova (2019) also examine the choice between documented and undocumented migration. They focus on how different migration policies affect this decision. They calibrate their model to the case of temporary migration from Thailand to more prosperous Asian countries in the late 1990s. In their calibrated model, the deportation rate is the most effective instrument, both to influence the choice between

documented and undocumented migration and to lower the stock of undocumented. Moreover, they find that policies aimed at increasing the wage of documented instead of undocumented workers can be more effective in affecting migration decisions than enforcement measures that reduce the wage of undocumented workers. Finally, they show that lengthening the duration of a documented worker's permit can be more effective in influencing the choice between documented and undocumented migration than tightening border controls that increase the cost of irregular migration.

Naiditch & Vranceanu (2017) use a global game approach, i.e. a game in a setting with incomplete information and noisy signals, to study the relationship between regular and irregular migration. They allow for network effects that facilitate migration to countries with a larger number of existing migrants. The main conclusions from the paper are that there exists a positive correlation between the number of regular and irregular migrants. Hence, if a destination country allows a large number of regular migrants, this destination country becomes more appealing to irregular migrants. Furthermore, if signals that migrants receive about the state of the economy of the destination country become less noisy, the probability of attracting a large number of migrants goes down. The reason is that if noise is high, in a given state of the economy more potential migrants will receive optimistic signals, which makes them decide to migrate. The network benefit acts as a multiplier of this effect.

In a recent study, Facchini and Testa (2021) develop a political agency model with an uneven distribution of gains from migration over voters in the destination country. Capital-rich voters prefer more cheap foreign workers, which implies under standard income distributions that the median prefers less migrants than the average voter. A two-stage game is played in which the politician in office first announces an official migration quota and the resources allocated to policy enforcement. There is uncertainty about the supply of migrants. Moreover, voters cannot perfectly observe the resources allocated to policy enforcement. In the next stage, voters observe the actual amount of migrants in the country (but not their supply nor the amount of resources spent on enforcement). Voters then decide whether to re-elect the current politician or to replace him. Facchini and Testa (2021) show that the politician in office has an incentive to set a strict migration quota to gain the support of the median voter. However, he underinvests in enforcement to admit more foreign workers as undocumented migrants, because of re-election concerns. Hence, in this setting political competition raises illegal immigration above the social optimum.

4. A Stylized Model

In this section we present the model that we have built to show the impact of (the expectation of) restrictive border measures. We do not model *why* migrants have some decision rules, but rather how the aggregate set of migrants' decision rules, in combination with the endogenous behaviour of smugglers, lead to a dynamic path of prices and aggregate flows; and on how those outcomes will be affected by policy interventions.

4.1. Set-up of the model

We propose a stylized model of a market for smuggling services. We simplify the problem considerably by assuming that smugglers only differ in their unit costs of smuggling, migrants only differ with respect to their willingness to pay for a transit and all smugglers offer exactly the same service.¹⁰ One reason to do this is that, as said above, empirical information is often simply lacking to calibrate a model that tries to keep the full spectrum of heterogeneity that in reality exists among migrants and among smugglers. A second reason is that we aim to demonstrate the dynamic patterns that our model generates under the minimum possible set of assumptions: we do not have to develop a complex black-box model to achieve this. This allows us, in the interpretation of the results, to identify the key characteristics of the market for smuggling, and the resulting policy implications, in a transparent and intuitive way. We add here that there is no reason to believe that, for example, heterogeneity among migrants or smugglers would eliminate these key mechanisms and the dynamic patterns that arise from them.

Our model has three main types of actors. Firstly, there is a certain large number of potential migrants present in the transit country (Turkey). Each of them is willing and able to pay an individual-specific maximum amount of money to make a crossing to a preferred destination country in Western Europe, through Greece, over the Aegean Sea. The differences in willingness to pay stem from differences between individuals and the circumstances they are in, which – as said – by themselves we do not model explicitly. Migrants have to decide whether to cross, and if so, when. These decisions depend on the current and future expected prices of a crossing, and on current and expected migration policies and enforcement measures, as these policies and measures affect the likelihood that the destination will be reached, against which price, and under which other relevant conditions.

Secondly, a large number of people may become active to smuggle migrants from Turkey to Greece over sea, with profits given by the difference between revenues and costs. Indeed, smugglers will incur costs, notably in the form of buying a boat and foregoing labor income from alternative activities. These costs are allowed to differ between the smugglers, again reflecting that smugglers are in reality a heterogeneous groups with different characteristics.

Thirdly, there are governments in transit countries and destination countries. Governments can – with the assistance of intergovernmental institutions such as the EU – implement migration policies and enforcement measures, such as the construction of border fences, intensification of border patrols, search and rescue missions, state-of-

¹⁰ Willingness to pay results from many individual characteristics and circumstances, such as wealth, capabilities and push factors.

emergency declarations, limits on the daily amount of entering migrants, restrictions on the nationalities of asylum seekers, border closures and so-called pushbacks. Some of these policies and measures are expected well in advance by the migrants in the transit country. Other measures may arrive unexpectedly over time.

We do not take into account the effect of Balkan-route-policy-measures on migration to Western Europe through alternative routes (such as via the Central Mediterranean). This limitation of our analysis may have consequences for our results if, in reality, it is easy to switch between different migration routes and if policy measures affect different routes differently. Furthermore, we abstract from the effect of policies on the inflow of migrants into Turkey. Allowing for this effect would change the response of cumulative crossings to policy measures in our model if these policy measures change the total number of migrants outside Turkey that are willing to migrate to Western Europe via Turkey.

4.1.1. Smugglers

There is a large number of potential smugglers. They incur a certain cost per person smuggled (the unit cost); these costs may be different for different smugglers. All smugglers deliver identical services. As a result, a smuggler cannot ask a higher price for a transit than the price of its competitors; otherwise demand for its smuggling service would be zero. Furthermore, each individual smuggler is small compared to the entire market, implying that he cannot increase the fare for smuggling services by constraining his supply. We consider two versions of the model, which we call a baseline and an alternative model specification. In the baseline version, smugglers can enter and exit the market whenever they want, at zero costs and without any delay. Hence, at each moment in time, all smugglers with a unit cost below the fare are active (they immediately enter as soon as the fare rises above their unit cost). And all others are not (they immediately exit as soon as the fare drops below their unit cost).

In the alternative specification, entry and exit is subject to some delay, e.g. because smugglers have to obtain boats first. Smugglers gradually enter at a finite rate as long as current profits are positive. Likewise, they gradually exit when losses are incurred. Hence, it can happen that some smugglers with a unit cost below the current fare are not (yet) active, because entry takes a while. Similarly, it is possible that smugglers with a unit costs above the fare are active, because exit is not immediate either. The delay with which entry and exit occurs is assumed to depend on the difference between the fare and the unit costs of the smuggler with the highest unit costs, reflecting that (potential) smugglers will try to react faster when there is more at stake in terms of foregone profits or losses incurred.

4.1.2. Migrants

At each instant of time, there is a number of potential migrants present in Turkey. This stock variable changes over time due to outflow (e.g. to Greece) and inflow of people (e.g. from Syria). As stated, migrants in Turkey differ from each other, and this translates into differences in their willingness to pay for a crossing to Greece. Only people whose willingness to pay is large enough relative to the price for smuggling services they will have to pay at the moment of travelling, will decide to go.

Indeed, migrants who have decided that they want to cross, must subsequently decide when to cross, and which smuggler to approach. Postponement of crossing may be attractive the fare is expected to fall. But waiting comes with costs as well, for instance as

a result of the possibility that more stringent migration policies or enforcement measures will be introduced soon. Moreover, everything else unchanged, future crossings are less attractive than current ones, because of impatience.

4.1.3. Non-monetary cost

Next to the monetary costs that the smugglers have to incur (e.g. by buying boats, buying fuel, paying bribes and foregoing alternative labor income or paying wages) there are additional costs (e.g. in terms of the risk of being apprehended or the risk of an accident). We refer to these costs as 'non-monetary costs'. They are affected by policy interventions; more stringent policies lead to higher non-monetary costs. These costs may also depend on the smuggling volume at a particular moment (e.g. because the risk of being apprehended by the police depends on the amount of boats per border guard); a larger number of crossings leads to lower non-monetary costs. It is important to make a distinction between non-monetary costs borne by the migrants and non-monetary costs borne by the smugglers. Smugglers will pass on these non-monetary costs to the migrants. Hence, they will be reflected in the fare. However, the non-monetary costs borne by the migrants are not included in the fare.

4.1.4. Market equilibrium

A market equilibrium is a situation in which supply of crossings and demand for crossings at any particular moment in time are equal to each other, and no agent (smuggler or migrant) has an incentive to change any of the decisions (including timing). This results in a time path of monthly arrivals in Greece and a time path of the price of a crossing. In the baseline model specification, supply of smuggling services is such that all smugglers with unit costs below the fare are active. The remaining smugglers (temporarily) exit the market, and may for instance return to their original profession. In the alternative version, the supply of smuggling services at each instant of time is determined by past entry and exit of smugglers, and gradually increases (or decreases) if current profits are positive (or negative).

Demand for smuggling at any moment in time is the result from (i) the total number of migrants that ultimately want to cross given their willingness to pay for crossing and the (monetary and non-monetary) cost of a transfer; and (ii) an intertemporal trade-off: each migrant chooses the time of crossing such that his or her net benefits (i.e. willingness to pay minus fare minus non-monetary cost) are maximized. This requires that for each migrant the expected net benefit of a crossing cannot be higher than what it is at the moment of crossing, at any alternative instant of time (otherwise, this particular migrant or refugee would rather go earlier or later, at a moment with higher net benefits). We can then characterize equilibrium on the demand side of the market as a price path for which it is true that no migrant can be better off by unilaterally changing the moment of crossing. Migrants with negative net benefits at any instant of time decide not to cross.

4.2. Three scenarios

We consider three different scenarios: 'no-policy', 'existing-policy' and 'additional funding'. In the *no-policy* scenario, migrants in Turkey expect that all borders will remain as open or closed as they are at that moment and that no additional policy interventions will occur in the future. We consider this as a relevant benchmark situation, against which to judge what the impact of real policies may have been; it is, for that purpose, not important how realistic this scenario is.

In contrast, in the existing-policy scenario, migrants expect from the beginning (i.e. January 2015) that more stringent policies will be introduced at some, relatively soon, moment in the future. This dramatically reduces the expected net benefit of more distant-future crossings. As a result, people who want to go eventually, have an incentive to do so as early as possible. This demand for early trips drives prices early on in the dynamic equilibrium up: the additional value for an early crossing, on top of satisfying impatience, is that it reduces the probability of not being able to cross at all. At each moment in time, the fare and the non-monetary costs add up to a level that equals the willingness to pay for the migrant who is in equilibrium just indifferent between crossing and not crossing. On the supply side of the market, the equilibrium condition that should simultaneously hold states that at any moment in time, all potential smugglers who can profitably operate given the price at that moment, will indeed be active. Hence, the increase in the price of early trips attracts more smugglers to the market initially.

In the existing-policy scenario, we include migration policies and enforcement measures in the non-monetary cost. Furthermore, we include the probability of apprehension as a separate component of the non-monetary costs of crossing. Changes in migration policies and enforcement measures are assumed to happen unexpectedly and are expected to stay in place permanently. Changes in the probability of apprehension are also assumed to occur unexpectedly. However, they are expected to remain in place only during the current month: for every month, smugglers and migrants form new expectations on this probability.

As we calibrate the model to match the outcomes of the policy scenario with the data, the no-policy benchmark scenario should in fact technically be considered as a counterfactual scenario.

4.3. Calibration

One exercise we need to do for the calibration is to translate non-monetary cost components into measures and units that make them useable in modelling trade-offs that actors make in the model. To that end, we construct an index that captures the stringency of migration policies and enforcement measures, on a unit scale (with 0 corresponding to a situation without policies or measures and 1 meaning fully closed borders). Furthermore, we have monthly data on the apprehension rate (the number of migrants apprehended by the Turkish Coast Guard as a share of the arrivals in Greece and the number of apprehended people). By subtracting the mean from this time series of apprehension rates, we obtain a second index, which captures the extraordinary (i.e. above average) probability of apprehension in each month. Both measures are converted into non-monetary cost components through multiplication by a scaling parameter. This scaling parameter makes it possible to determine the change in the fare that would have had the same effect on the time path of the crossings as a change in each of these two measures.

We also take into account the inflow of migrants into Turkey between 2015 and 2017. This inflow is modeled as an unexpected, exogenous increase in the number of migrants present in Turkey in each month, based on the actual data.

We calibrate the model by choosing the parameter values in order to minimize the sum of the squared deviations (a conventional measure of statistical fit) between the model

outcomes of the policy scenario and the following actual numbers, which were directly taken from the data:

- The maximum monthly arrival rate in Greece is equal to 212.168 people;
- This maximum arrival rate occurs in October 2015;
- The cumulative flow of migrants from Turkey to Greece between 1 January 2015 and 1 January 2020 is 1.2 million¹¹;
- The maximum price for a crossing in 2015 is 4.000 euro (which is the lower bound of the estimate of the highest price in the data).

Because of the correlation between the arrival rate on the one hand and the apprehension rate and policy measures on the other hand, it turns out to be hard to disentangle the fare and the non-monetary costs. Hence, the price path generated by the model should be interpreted as the sum of the fare and most of the non-monetary costs.

4.4. Results

The effect of existing policies

Figure 5 shows the time paths of the monthly arrivals of migrants in Greece from 2015 until 2017. The grey line depicts the actual number of migrants from the data. The solid black line is the outcome of the existing-policy scenario of the calibrated model. The dashed black line shows the outcome of the model in the no-policy scenario. The outcome of the calibrated model seems to match the data quite well (compare the solid black with the grey spike). In going from the solid to the dashed black line, we move from the simulation of what has actually happened, to a counterfactual benchmark scenario. In doing so, we keep the parameter values of the model constant, but remove all changes in policy and enforcement measures since January 1, 2015. Moreover, we impose that migrants do not expect the borders to be closed at all.

The dashed black line shows that in this counterfactual world without an expected border closure, and without increasingly more stringent migration policies and enforcement measures in response to the spike in the flow of migrants, the spike in arrivals in Greece would be much less pronounced. Migration would be more smoothly spread out over time. Without an expected closure of the border, it becomes less attractive to cross during times with an excessively high migration flow, because of the high fare. Hence, incentivizes migrants to wait for more quiet times. In turn, this leads to a lower fare, as shown in Figure 6, and less aggressive entry of new smugglers into the market. In both scenarios, the price goes down over time for two reasons. First, migrants with the highest willingness to pay cross first. Second, the equilibrium fare of later trips is lower to compensate for the disadvantages of postponing the crossing. The total amount paid to smugglers in the existing-policy scenario equals 3.2 billion euro, compared to 2.4 billion euro in the counterfactual no-policy scenario. Hence, total revenues of the smugglers are 0.8 billion euro *larger* in the existing-policy scenario.

Figure 7 shows the cumulative number of migrants that have entered Europe. By construction, the existing-policy scenario matches the number of 1.2 million migrants by

¹¹ International Organization for Migration (IOM), Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM); <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/yearly-compilation-of-arrivals-to-europe>.

the end of 2020. In the model, borders are effectively closed in April 2016, so that the cumulative flow remains constant from that moment onward. In the data, however, there are still 200.000 people who cross between April 2016 and the end of 2020. This explains the discrepancy between the existing-policy scenario of the model and the data. When comparing the existing-policy scenario (solid black line) with the counterfactual no-policy scenario (dashed black line), we see that in total 300.000 additional migrants would have crossed without the existing policies. This implies that existing policies have reduced the cumulative number of migrants by 20 percent (from 1.5 million in the counterfactual scenario to 1.2 million in reality). However, these policies have also *increased* the peak number of monthly arrivals by 200 percent (from 70.000 to 212.168).

Summarizing, our model outcomes suggest that existing policies have substantially increased the peak number of arrivals in Greece – due to so-called ‘now or never migration’ (cf. De Haas et al., 2019) – and have been much less effective in terms of reducing the cumulative number of crossings over the Aegean sea than what may be suggested by the drop in flow after the policies have been put in place. The peak is high partly because migrants anticipate the policies, and a naive visual inspection of volumes would therefore overestimate the policies’ effectiveness. Still, a 20 percent reduction of total volume is a significant effect.

Figure 5: Monthly arrivals in Greece

Figure 6: Fare

Note: The fare includes the non-monetary costs that are not captured by the two policy stringency indices.

Figure 7: Cumulative arrivals in Greece

The effect of additional funding in Turkey

We also examine what would have happened in an alternative policy scenario, in which the EU would have provided additional funding for migrants in Turkey. More specifically, we look at the effects of additional funding that would have reduced the willingness to pay for a crossing to Greece with 1.000 US\$ for each refugee or migrant in Turkey. The total amount of funding required to obtain this increase in willingness to pay cannot be estimated with our model. We leave this for future research. Figures 8-10 show the results. The solid black lines correspond to the scenario in which we have imposed the additional funding on top of the current policies. The dashed lines correspond to a scenario without the existing policies, but with the additional funding.

Figure 8 shows that the additional funding reduces the spike in migration, with 50 percent in the scenario with existing policies and with 75 percent in the scenario without existing policies, both compared to the actual number in the data. The price for smuggling services goes down as well, as can be seen by comparing Figure 9 with Figure 6. Finally, Figure 10 shows that the cumulative amount of migrants crossing to Greece goes down by half a million (that is 42 percent, compared to the 1.2 million from the data) in the scenario with additional funding on top of the existing policies (solid black line). In the scenario with additional funding but without existing policies (dashed black line), cumulative migration goes down by 200.000 (that is 17 percent).

Hence, our findings suggest that providing additional funding to migrants who are currently in Turkey would have reduced both the peak number of monthly arrivals and the cumulative number of migrants between January 1, 2015 and the end of 2020. Note, however, we have assumed that this additional funding did not attract new refugees or migrants to Turkey who would also have been willing to cross to Greece. Moreover, estimating the total costs of this policy requires information on the amount of funding required to reduce the willingness to pay for a crossing of each migrant in Turkey by 1000 US\$.

Figure 8: Monthly arrivals in Greece with additional funding in Turkey

Figure 9: Fare with additional funding in Turkey

Figure 10: Cumulative arrivals in Greece with additional funding in Turkey

5. Discussion

According to our model, spikes are related to the expectation of restrictive migration policies on the side of migrants (resulting in now or never migration) combined with a delay in market access of smugglers. If migrants would not expect restrictive migration policies, a similar (and possibly larger) number of migrants would have travelled from Turkey to Europe, but they would have arrived in a more gradual manner. In other words: restrictive migration policies have ambiguous effects: on the one hand they clearly result in spikes (perceived in 2015-2016 as a migration crisis), while on the other hand restrictive migration policies may have contributed to a lower aggregate volume of migration in the long run.

According to our model, financially supporting hosting countries for providing humanitarian and socio-economic aid to refugees has reduced the number of people who were willing to pay a smuggler in order to travel to Europe. In other words, the effects of providing funding for refugees in Turkey has had unambiguous, positive effects on reducing the volume of irregular migration towards Europe and deaths at the borders

It should be emphasized that our model does not pretend to capture the decision-making process of either people in need of international protection or of people considering to act as smugglers. We have abstracted from many aspects which are known to be relevant.

What our model does allow for is to examine the impact of restrictive migration policies. While policy makers and much of the academic literature assumes that restrictive policies reduce the flow of migrants, our analysis shows that the restrictive measures which migrants and smugglers expect considerably increase the flow before the introduction of restrictive policy measures, while resulting in a reduction only after their enforcement.

Including gender and age in the model would have refined the model because this sheds more light on group strategies (supra, 11). Our data did not allow us to address this aspect, but it should be kept in mind for future research.

Annex 1: Data

In total, 5 datasets were identified, compiled and used in this research. In the following section, a short explanation on each dataset, as well as justifications and other related notes are provided.

1. Number of migrants on the Balkan route 2011-2020

The phenomenon to be explained is the number of migrants and asylum seekers on the Balkan route in the period 2015-2016. For a qualitative analysis of the demographic characteristics, we include data on nationality, age, gender, class where available.

Among the total population that used the Balkan Route in 2015-2016, the five most important nationalities (Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Iran) were identified and two databases were compiled based on UNHCR, Frontex and IOM datasets.¹² One database includes daily arrivals and the other database includes monthly arrivals in the Balkan region.

Figure 11: Number of irregular border crossing detections (per nationality) at the Aegean Sea

Source: Frontex Risk Analysis Network (FRAN) data.

¹² UNHCR, Daily Estimated Arrivals through Western Balkans Route: <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/daily-estimated-arrivals-through-western-balkans-route>; Frontex, Western Balkans Annual Risk Analysis 2017: https://frontex.europa.eu/assets/Publications/Risk_Analysis/WB_ARA_2017.pdf; IOM, Nationalities of Migrants arriving to Italy and Greece in 2015: <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/greece-and-italy-nationalities-of-arrival-2015>.

2. Policy responses

The policy responses of countries along the Balkan route since 2015¹³ are a first factor that may impact the number of migrants and asylum seekers on the Balkan route. These policies can be gathered under two categories: national policies and bilateral/multilateral policies. For example, an N. Macedonian national policy intervention, facilitating a 72 hour “visa” (aka 72-hours paper) for migrants on 18 June 2015 triggered a bilateral policy response from Serbia and Hungary by initiating joint patrols at Serbia’s border with North Macedonia. Multilateral policies such as the EU-Turkey Joint Action Plan and the EU-Turkey Statement also may have had effects on the number of migrants. Within the ASILE project working package 5, a working paper (Tan & Vedsted-Hansen 2021) and two country reports outlining the policies in Turkey and Serbia were already published (Djurovic, Djurovic, & Spijkerboer, 2022; Ovacik, Ineli-Ciger, Ulusoy, & Spijkerboer, 2022). Together with those reports, existing literature has been reviewed. Relevant policies in all Balkan Route countries for the related period (see below for examples) were identified and compiled. Furthermore, to be able to use the compiled data in the model, policy responses have been coded as “border restriction” or “border closing” based on their impact on migrant mobility.

Figure 12: Border restrictions and closures on the Balkan route, compiled by the authors

- 17 June 2015, Hungary announces a plan to build a 175 km fence along the Serbian border.
- 29 June 2015, Joint patrols by Serbian, Hungarian and Frontex officers at the Serbia’s border with North Macedonia.
- 15 September 2015, Hungary: state of emergency announced. Construction of the 175 kilometer fence at the Serbian border completed.
- 17 September 2015, Croatia closes seven of its eight border roads with Serbia.
- 18 October 2015, Slovenia closes border and limits the entry to max 2.500 migrants per day from Croatia.

¹³ Continuation of data collection after 2016 is necessary in order to understand why the numbers on the Balkan route remained low since the EU-Turkey statement.

- 11 November 2015, Slovenia begins the construction of a fence at the Croatian border.
- 17 November 2015: Slovenia allows only asylum seekers from Syria, Iraq and Afghanistan to enter.
- 18 November 2015, Serbia, Croatia, N. Macedonia allow only asylum seekers from Syria, Iraq and Afghanistan to enter.
- 29 November 2015: EU-Turkey Joint Action Plan activated.
- February 2016: Croatia begins pushbacks towards Serbia.
- 9 March 2016, N. Macedonia, Croatia, Slovenia: Closed borders for all migrants, Balkan Route declared closed.
- 20 March 2016: EU-Turkey statement enters into effect.
- July 2016: Hungary begins pushbacks towards Serbia.
- April 2017: Rumania begins pushbacks towards Serbia.
- Pushbacks from Greece to Turkey have been a constant phenomenon, which may have varied in frequency.

3. Visa requirements in North Africa

The visa requirements of North-African countries for the five most important nationalities (Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Iran) since 2011 may have affected the number of people on the Balkan route.¹⁴ Syrians initially travelled to Europe via North Africa and Italy. The blocking of this option by the introduction of visa requirements in North Africa may have contributed to the build-up of demand for smuggling services on the Turkish west coast by diverting Syrian refugee migration towards Europe from the Central to the Eastern Mediterranean route.

We have collected data on visa policies from the DEMIG visa database for the period up until 2013/2014,¹⁵ and from the Passport Index for the current situation.¹⁶ We have acquired additional information from an expert in Egypt (Annex).

Syrian nationals

In 2011, Morocco and Tunisia required visa from Syrian nationals. Today, Egypt, Libya and Algeria also require visa from Syrian nationals. Visa requirements were introduced by Libya in January 2013, Egypt in July 2013, and Algeria in 2015.

In accordance with the solidarity policy followed by the Egyptian Muslim Brotherhood administration towards the Syrian revolt, no prior visa was required for Syrians entering Egypt. After the Muslim Brotherhood administration was toppled in July 2013, it became mandatory for Syrians to issue a prior visa (Annex).

¹⁴ This period exceeds the 2015-2016 spike which is the focus of the research, but this is necessary in order to test hypotheses related to possible shift from the Central Mediterranean to the Aegean in 2015, and back after 2016.

¹⁵ DEMIG (2015) DEMIG VISA, version 1.4, Full Edition. Oxford: International Migration Institute, University of Oxford, accessed 29 June 2022.

¹⁶ Passport Index, passportindex.org, accessed 29 June 2022.

Libya had no visa requirement for Syrian nationals until 2013 (DEMIG visa database). After the attack on the US diplomatic mission in Benghazi in September 2012, only families were allowed to enter, not single men. Since January 2013, visa was required (New Humanitarian 2013; COAR 2021, 8).

Until 2014, Algeria did not require visa from Syrian nationals (DEMIG visa database). It introduced visa requirement in 2015 (Rosenthal and Bogner 2017, 151).

Other nationalities

Nationals from the other four nationalities (Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq and Pakistan) needed visa for Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco in 2010 (DEMIG visa database) as well as now (Passport Index). For these nationalities the visa requirements of North African countries did not change.

4. Number of refugees and IDPs and funding

The number of (internal) IDP's and (external) refugees, in combination with the availability of humanitarian assistance in countries of origin and neighboring countries, is an indicator for the urge of refugees to undertake the onward journey to Europe. The hypothesis is that decreasing funds per refugee will lead to more demand for smuggling services in the direction of Europe. The data are limited to the top five nationalities that made use of the Balkan route, in the period 2011-2020, namely Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Iran.¹⁷

Figure 13: Syrian Refugees, Asylum Seekers and IDPs: Global and Turkey, stacked

Source: UNHCR.

¹⁷ This period exceeds the 2015-2016 spike which is the focus of the research, but this is necessary in order to test hypotheses related to the gradual erosion of reception and absorption capacity in the region.

Related datasets are collected from UNHCR and UNOCHA, cleaned and formatted for the purposes of the research.

Figure 14: Available international humanitarian funding for Turkey (per refugee/asylum seeker)

Source: UNHCR and UNOCHA.

5. Volume and price of smuggling on the Aegean 2015-2016

For the analysis we undertake, the volume and price of smuggling services on the Aegean in the period 2015-2016 are important data. Publicly available data on smuggling price are generally estimations or based on limited fieldwork and interviews such as “snapshots” of a single time and region (among others, see Yıldız, 2017; İçduygu, 2021; Europol & INTERPOL, 2016). However, the foreseen model requires longitudinal and higher frequency data inputs to understand the changes in the fees over the period. In order to get access to such data, we have tried to get in touch with European agencies in this field, but the response was limited. Frontex and EU Asylum Agency (EUAA) did not respond, while the Europol European Migrant Smuggling Centre (EMSC) informed us that “the topic does not link directly to the work” of this unit.¹⁸ An online meeting organized within the scope of the ASILE project with the migrant smuggling unit of Eurojust (31 March 2022) taught us that their human smuggling unit focuses on judicial cooperation in the field, but that they do not have price data. According to the Eurojust experts we consulted, this information is collected and analyzed by Frontex and shared with Europol.

¹⁸ Email by representative of Europol to the authors of 21 April 2021, on file with authors.

Figure 15: Arrivals of refugees/migrants in Greece from Turkey 2014-2022

Source: UNHCR.

Annex 2: Model

1. Set-up of the model

In this annex we provide the technical details of the model.

1.1. Smugglers

There is a continuum of S potential smugglers indexed by $s \in [0, S]$ who each can smuggle people according to a specific marginal cost function $k_s(q_s)$ with $k'_s(q_s) > 0$, where k_s denotes the marginal cost of smuggler s and q_s the amount of migrants smuggled by smuggler s . These cost functions may be different for different smugglers. By ranking the smugglers in ascending order on the basis of their lowest marginal costs $k_s(0)$, we can define the aggregate marginal cost function $k(q)$, with $k'(q) > 0$, which gives the unit costs per smuggled person if the migration flow equals q .¹⁹

All smugglers deliver qualitatively identical services. As a result, a smuggler cannot ask a price higher than the price of its competitors; otherwise demand for its smuggling services would be zero. Furthermore, each individual smuggler is small compared to the entire market, implying that a smuggler cannot increase the fare for smuggling services by constraining its supply.

We consider two versions of the model: a baseline and an alternative one. In the baseline version, smugglers can enter and exit the market whenever they want, at zero cost and without any delay. Hence, at each moment in time, all smugglers with unit cost below the fare are active (they immediately enter as soon as the price rises above their unit cost). And all others are not (they immediately exit as soon as the price drops below their unit cost). This implies that the smuggling supply function reads

$$k(q(t)) = p(t), \tag{1}$$

where q denotes the crossing rate (i.e. the number of crossings per unit of time), p the fare for smuggling services, and t is the time index.

Figure 16

Figure 16: provides an illustrative example with a linear marginal cost function.

¹⁹ Note that once we have ranked the smugglers on the basis of their lowest marginal costs, the amount of migrants smuggled by smuggler s , q_s , is determined by $k'_s(q_s) = k'_{s+1}(0)$.

Figure 16: Aggregate marginal cost function

In the alternative specification, entry and exit are subject to a delay, e.g. because smugglers have to obtain boats first. Smugglers gradually enter (exit) as long as current profits are positive (negative), according to²⁰

$$\dot{q}(t) = \begin{cases} \delta_0 q(t)[p(t) - k(q(t))] & \text{if } p(t) \geq k(q(t)), \\ \delta_1 q(t)[p(t) - k(q(t))] & \text{if } p(t) < k(q(t)), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\delta_0 > 0$ and $\delta_1 > 0$ are parameters that regulate the speed of entry and exit. Note that smugglers are myopic in the sense that they respond to *current* and *disregard* future profits. With the present specification, it is possible that some smugglers with unit cost below the current fare are not (yet) active, because entry takes a while. Similarly, it is possible that smugglers with unit cost above the fare are active, because exit is not immediate either.

1.2. Migrants

There is a continuum of $R(t)$ migrants indexed by $r \in [0, R(t)]$ present in Turkey. Migrants differ in terms of their willingness (and ability) to pay for crossing to Greece. Only people whose willingness to pay is large enough relative to the price for smuggling services, will decide to go. We denote the willingness to pay for (or: utility derived from) crossing by U and rank all migrants in Turkey in ascending order on the basis of their utility from crossing. This

²⁰ We use dots to denote time derivatives, e.g. $\dot{q}(t) \equiv q'(t)$.

yields a function $U(r)$ with $U'(r) > 0$, which gives the utility from crossing of individual r . Figure 17 provides an illustrative example with a linear utility function.

The number or stock of migrants in Turkey changes over time due to outflow to Greece or to other countries, and due to the inflow of people (e.g. from Syria). The net change over time is given by

$$\dot{R}(t) = [I(t) - y(t)] - q(t), \quad (3)$$

where I denotes the exogenous inflow and y the exogenous departures to countries other than Greece. The initial number of migrants in Turkey is taken as exogenously given.

Figure 17: Utility from crossing

Note: For migrants located to the left of the intersection of the utility line with the horizontal axis, utility from crossing is negative. They will decide not to cross, even if costs are zero.

Migrants who have decided to cross, must subsequently decide upon the moment of crossing. Postponement of crossing may be attractive if the fare is expected to fall. But waiting comes with costs as well, due to time discounting. The effective discount rate at time t , denoted by ρ , is given by the sum of the constant rate of pure time preference, $\tilde{\rho}$, and the instantaneous probability that the borders will be closed, $\mu(t)$:

$$\rho = \tilde{\rho} + \mu(t). \quad (4)$$

The first term takes into account that future crossings are less attractive than current ones because of impatience. The second term reflects the possibility that stringent migration policies or enforcement measures will be introduced in the future. The effective discount rate is assumed to be the same for all migrants.

1.3. Non-monetary costs

We denote the non-monetary cost per migrant at time t by $g(q(t), t)$. The time-dependence of g allows us to include (changes in) migration policy and enforcement measures. For example, rumors about gradually increasing stringency of border control can be captured by setting $g_t > 0$. Figure 18 provides an example in which non-monetary costs for a specific smuggling rate q_0 are expected to increase abruptly and permanently

at some point in the future, indicated by t_1 , due to more stringent policies. Note that the non-monetary costs borne by the smugglers are passed on to the migrants through the fare. In the theoretical model, p should be interpreted as the fare excluding those non-monetary costs.

The total costs per transfer as perceived by the migrants are given by the sum of the fare and the non-monetary costs:

$$h(q(t), t) = p(t) + g(q(t), t). \tag{5}$$

Note that the time paths of q and p are endogenously explained by the model. We assume that the total unit costs are increasing in the smuggling rate: $h_q > 0$.

Figure 18: Time path of the non-monetary migration costs

Note: The figure shows a time path of the non-monetary costs while keeping the crossing rate constant at q_0 .

2. Market Equilibrium

In this section, we define and characterize the market equilibrium for two different specifications of the supply side of the model. This results in two different systems of differential equations which describe the evolution of the market for smuggling services over time.

2.1. Definition

A market equilibrium is a situation in which the supply of crossings and the demand for crossings at any particular moment in time are equal to each other, while from neither the static instantaneous, nor the dynamic perspective, any actor has an incentive to unilaterally change behavior. This results in a time path of monthly arrivals in Greece and a time path of the fare. In the baseline version, supply of smuggling services is such that all smugglers with unit costs below the fare are active. The remaining smugglers (temporarily) exit the market, and may for instance return to their original profession. In the alternative version, the supply of smuggling services at each instant of time is

determined by past entry and exit of smugglers, and gradually increases (decreases) if current profits are positive (negative).

An individual migrant r who has decided to migrate, maximizes the present value of the net benefit of the transfer

$$[U(r) - p(t) - g(q(t), t)]e^{-\rho t}, \quad (6)$$

by choosing the crossing time t , while taking the time paths of p and g as given. Note that a migrant may also decide not to migrate at all, namely if the net present value of making a transfer is negative at each moment in time.

A market equilibrium is defined as a time path of the crossings, $q(t)$, and an associated time path of the total costs, $h(t) = p(t) + g(t)$, that makes each migrant with non-negative net benefits indifferent between migrating at different moments in time. In the baseline supply specification, the equilibrium time path of supply is such that instantaneous profits of the smugglers at any point in time are maximized, but due to free entry only reach a zero level (the required compensation for not being able to do the regular job, and for incurring risks, is treated as a cost for the zero-profit condition). In the alternative supply specification, supply is a state variable given by past entry and exit decisions and increases (decreases) over time if profits are positive (negative).

2.2. Characterization

We use optimal control theory to determine the market equilibrium. Intuitively, the main conditions that need to be satisfied in the equilibrium are: (i) The benefits of a transfer are equal to the total costs of a transfer, including the opportunity costs of going now rather than at another moment. (ii) The return to delaying a particular transfer – in terms of a higher net benefit – should be equal to the effective discount rate that represents disutility of waiting due to impatience, to make migrants indifferent between migrating now and in the future.

We restrict attention to functional forms of the utility and cost functions that guarantee the existence and uniqueness of a market equilibrium. We determine the market equilibrium by converting problem (6) of an individual migrant who chooses the optimal time of a crossing into the equivalent problem of a ‘collective migrant’ who maximizes²¹

$$\int_0^{\infty} [U(R(t)) - p(t) - g(t)]q(t)e^{-\rho t} dt, \quad (7)$$

by choosing a time path for the smuggling rate $q(t)$ subject to $\dot{R}(t) = [I(t) - y(t)] - q(t)$, $R(t) \geq 0$, $q(t) \geq 0$ and $R(0) = R_0$, taking the time paths of p and g as given. In this specification, $U(R(t))$ equals the maximum willingness to pay for a trip at time t . We have left out the argument q in the non-monetary cost function g to emphasize that the

²¹ The ‘collective migrant’ can be seen as an institution that determines if and when every individual migrant crosses in order to maximize total utility of all migrants, which results in a time path of the smuggling rate. Just like individual migrants, this institution takes the time paths of the fare and the non-monetary costs as given. It can be shown that the solution to the collective migrant problem coincides with the smuggling rate which results from the solutions to the optimization problems of the individual migrants. Hence, the two optimization problems are said to be equivalent.

collective migrant takes the time path of g as given. The time paths of I and y are exogenous.

We now have arrived at a standard dynamic optimization problem which can be solved by using optimal control theory. The current-value Hamiltonian reads

$$\mathcal{H} = [U(R(t)) - p(t) - g(t)]q - \lambda(t)[(I(t) - y(t)) - q(t)], \quad (8)$$

where λ is the co-state variable of R . The necessary conditions for an optimum are given by:

$$[U(R(t)) - p(t) - g(q, t) - \lambda(t)]q(t) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$U'(R(t))q(t) = -\dot{\lambda}(t) + \rho\lambda(t). \quad (10)$$

Condition (9) requires that if $q(t) > 0$, then $U(R(t)) = p(t) + g(q, t) + \lambda(t)$, stating that at each moment in time at which crossing takes place, the crossing rate will be chosen such that the utility of a transfer, $U(R(t))$, equals the sum of the fare and the non-monetary costs, $p(t) + g(q, t)$, plus the opportunity costs of going now rather than at a different moment, $\lambda(t)$. Furthermore, if $U(R(t)) < p(t) + g(q, t) + \lambda(t)$, no crossing takes place.

Condition (10) can be rewritten as

$$\dot{\lambda}(t) = \rho\lambda(t) - U'(R(t))q(t), \quad (11)$$

which is a so-called *Keynes-Ramsey-Hotelling rule* that needs to be satisfied in order to make migrants indifferent between crossing at different moments in time: the return to delaying a particular crossing – in terms of a higher net benefit – should be equal to the effective discount rate. The opportunity cost of going now rather than in the future, though, grows at a rate slower than the rate of time preference (captured by the first term on the right-hand side), as the utility of a transfer goes down when less migrants are left as those with the highest willingness to pay cross first (captured by the second term). The reason is that if migrants with a relatively low willingness to pay prefer to wait as their net benefit of crossing is growing over time at a rate higher than the effective rate of time preference as long as migrants with a higher willingness to pay have not yet crossed.

The dynamical system that characterizes the market equilibrium depends on the specification of the supply side of the model. We will discuss the baseline and the alternative supply specification in turn. In both specifications, we assume that not all migrants present in Turkey ultimately want to cross to Greece and that the exogenous inflow and outflow of people converges to zero in the long run.

Baseline Supply Specification

In the baseline supply specification, the level of supply equalizes the fare and marginal costs at each instant of time, i.e. $p = k(q)$. It can be shown that the market equilibrium converges to a steady state in which $\dot{q}(t) = \dot{R}(t) = q(t) = 0$. By combining (9)-(10) and using the equation for the evolution of the number of refugees, we obtain the following non-autonomous system of first-order differential equations in q and R , which describes the market equilibrium:

$$\dot{q}(t) = -\frac{\rho[U(R(t)) - k(q(t)) - g(q(t), t)] + g_t(q(t), t)}{k_r(a(t)) + a_r(a(t), t)}, \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{R}(t) = [I(t) - y(t)] - q(t). \quad (13)$$

Without the expected future introduction of binding, prohibitively stringent migration policies or enforcement measures,²² we have two additional boundary conditions: $R(0) = R_0$ and $q(\infty) = 0$.^{23 24}

Alternative Supply Specification

In the alternative specification, supply of smuggling services is treated as a state variable which gradually increases (decreases) over time if profits are positive (negative). It can be shown that the market equilibrium converges to a steady state with $\dot{p}(t) = \dot{q}(t) = \dot{R}(t) = q(t) = 0$, where $p(t) = k(q(t))$. By combining (2), (9), (10), and using the equation for the evolution of the number of refugees, we obtain the following non-autonomous system of first-order differential equations in p , q and R , which describes market equilibrium:

$$\dot{p}(t) = \rho[U(R(t)) - p(t) - g(q(t), t)] + g_q(q(t), t)\dot{q}(t) - g_t(q(t), t), \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{q}(t) = \begin{cases} \delta_0 q(t)[p(t) - k(q(t))] & \text{if } p(t) \geq k(q(t)), \\ \delta_1 q(t)[p(t) - k(q(t))] & \text{if } p(t) < k(q(t)), \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{R}(t) = [I(t) - y(t)] - q(t). \quad (16)$$

Without the expected future introduction of binding, prohibitively stringent migration policies or enforcement measures, we have three additional boundary conditions:

$$R(0) = R_0, q(0) = q_0 \text{ and } p(\infty) = k(0).$$

3. Policy

In this section, we formulate three policy scenarios and construct two policy stringency indices in order to examine the effects of different types of migration policies in our model.

3.1. Three Scenarios

We consider three different scenarios: 'no-policy', 'existing-policy' and 'additional funding'. In the no-policy scenario, migrants in Turkey expect that all borders will remain as open or closed as they are at that moment and that no additional policy interventions will occur in the future. We consider this a relevant benchmark situation, against which to judge what the impact of real policies may have been.

²² If permanent, prohibitively stringent migration policies or enforcement measures are expected to be implemented at some future finite time t_1 , the end time becomes exogenous and equal to t_1 , q no longer converges to zero, and the end condition on utility becomes $U(R(t_1)) = k(q(t_1)) + g(q(t_1), t_1)$.

²³ If $\rho[U(R(\infty)) - k(0) - g(0, \infty)] + g_t(0, \infty) = 0$ does not have a solution for $R(\infty) \geq 0$, we get $R(t) = 0$ for $t \geq T > 0$, implying that all migrants or refugees cross in finite time. In this case, $\dot{q}(T) < 0$. Note that we have excluded this case by assumption.

²⁴ To simplify the exposition, we slightly abuse notation by writing $q(\infty) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} q(t) = 0$.

On the contrary, in the existing-policy scenario, migrants expect from the beginning (i.e. January 2015) that more stringent policies will be introduced at some, relatively soon, moment in the future. More specifically, people expect the borders to be closed within a month. This implies that the instantaneous probability that the borders will be closed, $\mu(t)$, is infinitely large for any $t \geq 1$.²⁵ This reduces the expected net benefit of future crossings to zero. As a result, people who want to go eventually, try to go as early as possible.

In the existing-policy scenario, we include migration policies and enforcement measures in the non-monetary cost. Furthermore, we include the probability of apprehension as a separate component of the non-monetary costs of crossing. Changes in migration policies and enforcement measures are assumed to happen *unexpectedly* and are expected to stay in place permanently. Changes in the probability of apprehension are also assumed to occur unexpectedly. However, they are expected to remain in place only during the current month.

Finally, we consider an *additional funding* scenario, where we increase the amount of funding per migrant or refugee in Turkey. We consider two sub-scenarios with additional funding: one with and one without existing policies.

3.2. Stringency Indices

We have constructed an index that captures the time path of the stringency of migration policies and enforcement measures, on a unit scale (with 0 corresponding to a situation without policies or measures and 1 meaning fully closed borders), denoted by $s(t)$. A brief description of the policy interventions on which this index is based can be found in Annex 1. The time path of the policy stringency index is shown in Figure 19.

Furthermore, we have monthly data on the apprehension rate (the number of apprehended people as a share of the arrivals in Greece and the number of apprehended people). See Figure 20. By subtracting the mean apprehension rate from this time series, we obtain a time path for the apprehension risk index, which captures the extraordinary (i.e. above average) probability of apprehension in each month and is denoted by $a(t)$.

We convert the policy stringency index and the apprehension risk index into non-monetary costs components by multiplying each of them with a scaling parameter. These two scaling parameters make it possible to determine the change in the fare that would have had the same effect on the time path of the crossings as a change in each of these two measures.

²⁵ Results for the case with a finite instantaneous probability of border closure are available from the authors upon request.

Figure 19: Policy stringency index

Note: The index is constructed based on expert judgments about the impact of implemented policy changes on mobility of migrants over the period 2015-2017.

Figure 20: Apprehension rate

Note: The apprehension rate is calculated as the number of apprehended irregular migrants by the Turkish Coastal Guard, divided by the sum of the amount of arrivals in Greece and the number of apprehended irregular migrants. Sources: The number of apprehended irregular migrants is reported by the Turkish Coastal Guard, (<https://en.sg.gov.tr/irregular-migration-statistics>); monthly arrivals in Greece are taken from the International Organization for Migration (<https://data.humdata.org/dataset/yearly-compilation-of-arrivals-to-europe>).

4. Functional Forms and Calibration

In order to run model simulations, we postulate functional forms for the utility, costs and supply functions in our model. Furthermore, we calibrate the model with data about monthly arrivals and crossing prices.

4.1. Functional Forms

We use the following linear functional forms:

$$U(R) = \mu_0 + \mu_1 R, \quad (17)$$

$$k(q) = \kappa_0 + \kappa_1 q, \quad (18)$$

$$g(q, t) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 q + f(t), \quad (19)$$

where $f(t)$ denotes the time path of the sum of the policy stringency index and the apprehension risk index, scaled by the parameters ω_s and ω_a :

$$f(t) = \omega_s s(t) + \omega_a a(t). \quad (20)$$

We approximate the differential equations (12)-(13) and (14)-(16) with difference equations by using Euler's method with time intervals of one month. Similarly, we use monthly data to construct a time series for (20).

4.2. Calibration

We calibrate the model by choosing the parameter values in order to minimize the sum of the squared deviations between the model outcomes of the policy scenario and the following actual numbers, from the data:

- The maximum monthly arrival rate in Greece is equal to 212.168 people;
- This maximum arrival rate occurs in October 2015;
- The cumulative flow of migrants from Turkey to Greece between 1 January 2015 and 1 January 2020 is 1.2 million;
- The maximum price for a crossing in 2015 is 4.000 euro (which is the lower bound of the estimate of the highest price in the data).

Because we calibrate the model to match the outcomes of the policy scenario with the data, the no-policy and additional funding scenarios should be considered as a counterfactual.

Our minimization procedure yields parameter values presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameter values

Parameter	Description	Value
μ_0	Vertical intercept utility function (in €)	-4,702.9
μ_1	Slope utility function (in €/1000 crossings)	1.5363
$\kappa_0 + \gamma_0$	Vertical intercept marginal costs (monetary and non-monetary costs together, in €)	1,107.7
$\kappa_1 + \gamma_1$	Slope of the marginal cost function (monetary and non-monetary costs together, in €/1000 crossings)	9.1720
δ_0	Entry parameter	$3.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$
δ_1	Exit parameter	0.0011
ω_a	Scaling parameter of the apprehension risk index	60.3438
ω_s	Scaling parameter of the policy stringency index	93.1207

Note that, due to the linear form of the supply function (18) and the non-monetary cost function (19), it is not possible to make a distinction between the intercept and slope parameters of these two functions. This explains why the combined effects of the two show up in Table 1. Furthermore, the scaling parameters for the policy stringency and the apprehension risk indices are rather low. The increase in the policy stringency over time from the beginning of 2015 until the end of 2016 is estimated to be equivalent to an increase in the fare for smuggling services of around 93 euro per crossing. And the difference between the minimum and maximum apprehension risk is estimated to be worth only 29 euro per crossing, whereas the average price over this period is equal to 2,783 euro per crossing. There are at least two potential reasons for these small numbers. First, the effect of policy and apprehension risk changes over time is attributed to $\kappa_1 + \gamma_1$, because of the correlation between these indices and the crossing rate. This implies that the fare generated by the model should be interpreted as the price including most of the non-monetary costs. Second, the policy measures (apart from the expected full border closure) and the apprehension risk just have a small effect on the migration flows.

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